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Effect of Concentrate Feeding Regimens on the Morphometric, Gastrointestinal Tract Parts and Visceral Organs Weight of Grasscutter Fed *Pennisetum Purpureum*.

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Abstract

The study was designed to determine the effect of concentrate feed regimes on the morphometric indices and gastrointestinal tract (GIT) parts weights of grasscutter fed *pennisetum purpureum* as basal feed. Twenty (20) grasscutters between the ages of 3-4 months were equalized by weight and used in a Completely Randomized Design. Five different treatment regimes with a treatment having four replicates with an animal serving as a replicate were used. The treatments were; treatment 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 for 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9% respectively of concentrate feed which were served at their weekly live weight. Parameters measured included, Entire GIT, oesophagus, stomach, small intestine, caecum and colon/rectum for morphometric characteristics and also for weighed. Results obtained showed that, the entire (GIT) and some of its components (empty stomach, small intestine, caecum and colon/rectum) expressed as percentages of their live weight differed in all the treatments apart from Oesophagus. The average length of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) of the grasscutter varied from 335.00 to 411.00 cm and it was significant. The longest length was in T₅ while the shortest was in T₁. It was observed in this study that the relative weights of entire GIT and its components (empty small intestine, caecum and colon/Rectum in T₅ had a superior weight and they were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from other treatments. These findings generally suggested that the feeding regimes had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on some morphometric traits and the relative weights of the grasscutter GIT.

Key words: Concentrate supplement regimes, Morphometric characteristics, organ weights, Grasscutters, *Pennisetum purpureum*

Introduction

The grasscutter is a wild herbivorous rodent, which lives mainly on grass and other succulent forages. It is related to other herbivorous rodents like the African porcupine, the brush-tailed porcupine, the guinea pig and the chinchilla (Baptist and Mensah, 1986; NRC, 1991). The gastro-intestinal tract of grasscutter combines the functions of the monogastric and ruminant digestive tracts (Olomu *et al.*, 2003). It is suggested that the grasscutter would require the same 41 amino acids ordinarily required by other monogastric animals, 13 essential amino acids which cannot be synthesized enough by the body system and the other non-essential which can be synthesized by the body system enough to meet to up dietary requirements. The grasscutter's gastro-intestinal tract is adapted to handle high fibre materials because of the presence of a large caecum which houses some microbes that help in the digestion of cellulose. The presence of cellulolytic bacteria in the caecum of the grasscutter has been shown by Hammer, (1992). Animals with this system are referred to as hind-gut fermenters, meaning that feed is broken down by bacteria at the end of the digestive system. The microbial activity of the caecum is of great importance for the processes of digestion and nutrient utilization from fibrous material (Carabano and Piquer, 1998).

Grasscutter exhibit some features of the ruminant by consuming large quantity of forages (leaves and stems) and fermenting it in the gut chamber that harbours microbes. B-vitamins are a useful by product of the process. The difference is that whereas, for the ruminants the rumen is at the beginning of the gut, and the products of fermentation are absorbed from the rumen and lower gut, the caecum is towards the end of the

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gut, and the grasscutter has to re-ingest fermentation products through the mouth, that is, they also practice *coprophagy/caecotrophy* like the rabbit. The digestive system of the grasscutter is made up of the mouth, stomach, small intestine, caecum and large intestine.

The grasscutter is an herbivorous animal with a wide nutritional intake. The major part of its diet is composed of grasses with fairly high crude fibre content. It can apparently tolerate a certain level of tannin found in leaves and bark as well as cyanogenic glycosides present in green maize, sorghum and Manihot earlier reported (Ewer, 1969). Under-altered condition, the grasscutter is able to adapt itself to another diet. Ewer, (1969) also reported earlier on that, shrubs and bushes growing in the enclosure where grasscutters are kept were neglected at first but were later-eaten readily. They always prefer grasses with lots of moisture and some soluble carbohydrate (Ajayi and Tewe, 1980; Onadeko, 1996; Agbelusi, 1997). They equally eat fallen fruits, nuts and many kinds of cultivated crops (Fitzinger, 1995). The grasscutter is a wasteful feeder, cutting the grass at a characteristic angle with its very powerful incisors to cut the more nutritious succulent inner nodes, leaving behind scattered pieces on the ground (Ewer, 1969; Asibey, 1974b). Grasscutter can equally be raised on the backyard to provide meat for the family by feeding them kitchen left-over (Agbelusi, 1997; Addo, 1997). Fitzinger, (1997) reported that, they eat grasses and other foods with their incisors, producing a chattering sound that is relatively loud and very distinguishable.

All the activities that grasscutter performs require the use of energy which is the products of digestion and subsequent oxidation of nutrients derived from the different types of food. These food materials need to be broken down either by enzymatic or microbial activities in the intestinal lumen of the different segments of the GIT before they can be absorbed. These food materials according to Olusanya and Olowo (1988) are necessary to build, repairs tissues and regulates body processes. The macroscopic studies of the GIT of other conventional animal species like sheep, cattle, pig, horse and dog (Sisson and Grossman, 1975) and for rodents like rats, rabbit and mouse (Caster *et al.*, 1956; Rudolf and Stromberg 1976) and of recent grasscutter (Byanet *et al.*, 2008) have been documented but not on the effect of feeding on the different segments of the GIT and the organs. It was on this basis that, the study was designed on the morphometric indices and weights of the different GIT parts and visceral organs using concentrate feeding regimes and elephant grass as a basal feed.

Materials and methods

Experimental Animals and Housing

Twenty (20) grower Grasscutters between the ages of 3-4 months purchased at Benin Republic were used for the feeding regime trial which lasted 24 weeks (168 days). The grasscutters were acclimatized for two weeks before the commencement of the study. The grasscutters were individually housed in concrete pens measuring 50 x 50 x 40 cm (length x width x height), open at the top. The top was partly covered to create a darkened area. Each pen was provided with a feeder and a drinker. These pens were constructed inside a building built with a half wall and roof with corrugated iron sheet to prevent direct sunlight and rain.

Experimental Design and Duration of Study

Twenty (20) grower Grasscutters were randomly assigned to the five feeding regime treatments in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The study had five (5) treatments and four replicates per treatment, with each animal serving as a replicate. The grasscutters were individually fed in their various experimental units and the study lasted for 24 weeks (168 days).

Experimental Diet

The concentrate supplement was formulated to obtained 18% crude protein and Metabolizable energy of 2961.47 kcal/kg with the ingredients as shown in Table 1. This diet was served daily in their feeding trough at levels of 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9% of their live weekly body weight. The elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*)

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was wilted overnight about 18 hours, chopped, weighed using a Camry top loading weighing scale and fed unrestricted in mangers to the grasscutters.

Table 1: Composition of concentrate feed

Ingredients	%
Maize	58.41
Soybean meal	27.59
Rice offal	10.00
Bone meal	3.00
Vitamin-min-premix*	0.50
Common salt	0.50
Total	100.00
Calculated nutrients composition.	
Crude Protein	18.00
Metabolizable Energy (/kcal/kg)	2961.47
Crude fibre (%)	6.97
Calcium (%)	1.16
Phosphorus (%)	0.89

* Each 1kg of vitamin/mineral premix manufactured by BEAUTS Co. Inc. Man, U.S.A., contains Vitamin A 220,000, Vitamin D 66,000, Vitamin E 44, 014; Vitamin K 88 mg; Vitamin B 12; 0.76 mg; Niacin 1122 mg, Calcium 27%, Phosphorus 10%, Iron 0.6%, Zinc 0.35%, manganese 0.25%, Copper 0.06%; Iodine 0.002%, Cobalt 26 ppm, Selenium 4 pp. ME = Metabolizable Energy

Experimental Procedure

At the commencement of the experiment (1st week), all the animals were provided with antistress (Vitalyte) agents 2 g in a small concrete container used in serving them drinking water. They were also dewormed and given coccidiostat using piperazine citrate and proccox respectively. Elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*), were cut and allowed to be wilted for about 18 hours, chopped and was fed *ad libitum* as basal diet. Water was also supplied *ad libitum*. The grasscutters were individually weighed using Camry toploading weighing scale approximated to two decimal places, grouped into five in such a way to ensure uniformity of initial body weights in all the groups and allotted to different treatments in agreement with the design of the study. The average weight per group was 725 g and the animals were individually housed in their pens. The animals were weighed weekly during the growth study of 24 weeks. All pens were cleaned daily. Weighed amounts of feed were offered to each animal in the morning. The following morning the left over feed was weighed, after removing faecal and other contaminants.

Data Collection/Parameter Measured

At the end of the study, the animals were starved overnight so as to reduce contamination when opening up of the abdominal cavity. The parts to be studied were properly cut in their various segments, emptied and the visceral organs were properly removed, washed and weighed with a sensitive digital weighing balance and measured with a meter ruler. The entire GIT, oesophagus, stomach, small intestine, caecum and colon/rectum were used for morphometric characteristics and their weight recording. The cuts length were expressed as percentage of the entire gastrointestinal tract length while the cut weights were expressed as percentages of live weights

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using MINITAB 16 statistical software and where significant means was indicated, they were separated using Fishers LSD method as contained in the statistical package.

Results and Discussion

The effect of concentrate supplement feeding regime on morphometric measurements of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) is presented in Table 2. The oesophagus length, small intestine length and caecum length expressed as percentage of the entire gastrointestinal tract length did not differ significantly ($P>0.05$) between the dietary treatments. Whereas the morphometric characteristics of the entire GIT length, stomach and colon/rectum were significantly different ($P<0.05$) between the feeding regime treatments. The GIT length of grasscutters were similar ($P>0.05$) in $T_1 - T_4$ except T_5 . The stomach length of the grasscutters in T_1 were significantly ($P<0.05$) different from T_4 and T_5 but did not differ ($P>0.05$) from those in T_2 and T_3 . The measurement of the colon/rectum length showed a similarity ($P>0.05$) in T_1 , T_2 and T_4 while T_2 , T_3 , T_4 and T_5 were also similar ($P>0.05$).

Table 3 shows the effects of the treatments on the gastrointestinal tract parts. With the exception of the oesophagus weight, the weight of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), empty stomach, empty small intestine, empty caecum, and empty colon/rectum expressed as percentages of live weights were significantly different ($P<0.05$) between the dietary treatments. The entire gastrointestinal tract (GIT) of grasscutters in T_5 were significantly ($P<0.05$) different from all other treatments which were all similar ($P>0.05$). The oesophagus values of the grasscutters were not significantly ($P>0.05$) different between the treatments. The relative empty stomach weights of grasscutters fed T_1 , T_2 and T_5 were comparable ($P>0.05$) to each other but differed significantly ($P<0.05$) from T_3 and T_4 which were also similar ($P>0.05$) to T_2 and T_5 . The average weights of the empty small intestine of the grasscutters followed the same pattern of significant like the full GIT. The caecum of the grasscutters fed the different feeding regime were all alike in weight except those fed T_4 regime which however, were similar ($P>0.05$) to T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 . Empty colon /rectum weights T_5 was significantly higher ($P<0.05$) than all others treatments. The grasscutters fed T_1 , T_2 and T_4 feeding regime were similar ($P>0.05$) but differed ($P<0.05$) from T_3 .

The effect of concentrate supplement feeding regime on visceral organs weight is presented in Table 4. The weight of visceral organs namely; liver, kidney, heart, spleen and gall bladder expressed as percentages of grasscutter body weight were not significantly different ($P>0.05$) among the feeding regime treatments while the lung and the pancreas weights of the grasscutters weight were significantly different ($P<0.05$) among the treatments. The grasscutters lungs weight in T_4 were significantly higher ($P<0.05$) than those in T_1 and T_2 but similar to T_3 and T_5 . The lungs weight in T_1 , T_2 and T_3 were similar ($P>0.05$) as well as those of T_2 , T_3 and T_5 . The pancreas weight of T_1 , T_2 and T_5 were significantly ($P<0.05$) higher than T_3 and T_4 which were only similar ($P>0.05$) to T_5 .

Table 2: Effect of concentrate supplement feeding regime on the morphometric of the gastrointestinal tract of grasscutter.

Organ Lengths*	$T_1(1\%)$	$T_2(3\%)$	$T_3(5\%)$	$T_4(7)$	$T_5(9\%)$	SEM
GIT (cm)	335.00 ^b	352.50 ^{ab}	368.00 ^{ab}	387.00 ^{ab}	411.00 ^a	18.48
Oesophagus	3.75	4.11	4.08	3.88	3.40	0.39
Stomach	3.75 ^a	2.40 ^{ab}	3.53 ^{ab}	2.97 ^{bc}	2.67 ^c	0.19
Small Intestine	47.77	50.21	44.71	48.24	45.92	2.47
Caecum	9.57	4.39	6.99	5.65	6.93	1.49
Colon/Rectum	33.62 ^b	37.87 ^{ab}	40.40 ^a	39.25 ^{ab}	39.89 ^a	1.69

*% of GIT length

a, b and c means within rows with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p>0.05$), SEM= Standard Error of mean, GIT= Gastrointestinal tract,

Table 3: Gastrointestinal tract weight of grasscutters fed concentrate feeding regime.

GIT weight (% LW)	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_5	SEM
Empty GIT (Wt)	3.33 ^b	3.30 ^b	2.82 ^b	2.77 ^b	4.07 ^a	0.19
Oesophagus (Wt)	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.19	0.06	0.061

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Empty Stomach (Wt)	0.50 ^a	0.34 ^{ab}	0.27 ^b	0.28 ^b	0.36 ^{ab}	0.05
Empty small Intestine (Wt)	0.87 ^b	1.03 ^b	0.92 ^b	0.97 ^b	1.28 ^a	0.11
Empty Caecum (Wt)	0.89 ^{ab}	0.77 ^{ab}	0.83 ^{ab}	0.55 ^b	0.97 ^a	0.03
Empty Colon/ Rectum (Wt)	1.04 ^b	1.10 ^b	0.77 ^c	0.98 ^b	1.39 ^a	0.03

a, b, c and d means within rows with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p>0.05$), SEM= Standard Error of mean, LW. = Live weight, Wt = weight.

Table 4: Effect of concentrate supplement feeding regime on the visceral organs weight.

Visceral Organ (%LW)	T ₁ (1%)	T ₂ (3%)	T ₃ (5%)	T ₄ (7%)	T ₅ (9%)	SEM
Liver weight	1.27	1.19	1.62	1.24	1.30	0.14
Kidneys weight	0.33	0.32	0.25	0.31	0.33	0.02
Lungs weight	0.52 ^c	0.54 ^{bc}	0.69 ^{abc}	0.87 ^a	0.83 ^{ab}	0.09
Heart weight	0.39	0.42	0.40	0.42	0.48	0.06
Pancreas weight	0.04 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.03 ^b	0.03 ^b	0.04 ^{ab}	0.003
Spleen weight	0.11	0.14	0.11	0.08	0.15	0.03
Gall bladder weight	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.01

a, b, and c means within rows with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p>0.05$), SEM= Standard Error of mean, LW. = Live weight

The average length of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) of the grasscutter in this study varied from 335.00 to 411.00 cm and it was significant. The longest length was in T₅ while the shortest was in T₁. The length was slightly longer than 343.1 cm (Olomu, *et al.*, 2003). The measurements of each of the GIT constituents namely Oesophagus, small intestine, and caecum were comparable among the treatments while the stomach and the colon differed ($P<0.05$) among the treatments. The morphometric value of the stomach, small intestine, caecum, colon are comparable with 3.35-3.6 cm (stomach), 50-52.6 cm (small intestine), 5.5-7.8 cm (caecum), and 33-38.4 cm (colon/rectum) recorded by (Olomu, *et al.*, 2003). They were also comparative to the values recorded by Byanet *et al.*, (2008) apart from the caecum length (19-22 cm) which was longer than 8-17 cm recorded by them when they studied the macroscopic structure of the grasscutter gastrointestinal tract. It was however, observed numerically that, the caecum length in relation to live weights of the grasscutter presented a definite picture of the extent to which the feeding regimes affected this organ though not statistically significant. As observed from the results on the table, grasscutters fed 1% concentrate feed supplement recorded the highest value of 9.57%. The increased proportion of the caecum for grasscutters in this treatment could be explained to be as a result of compensatory growth of this organ to accommodate the intake of forage consumed by the animals. These findings generally suggested that the feeding regimes had a significant effect ($P<0.05$) on some morphometric traits of the grasscutter GIT.

The entire gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and some of its components (empty stomach, empty small intestine, empty caecum and colon/rectum) expressed as percentages of their live weight differed in all the treatments apart from Oesophagus and no particular sequence was followed. It was observed in this study that the relative weights of entire GIT and its components (empty small intestine, empty caecum and empty colon/Rectum) in T₅ had a superior weight and they were significantly ($P<0.05$) different from other treatments, which could be attributed to the high feed consumption which might have led to more crude fibre (CF) intake which was responsible for the increase in size and the weight of the various segments of the grasscutters as an adaptation to accommodate more feed. The variation within these values could also be attributed to the level of development of the digestive system of each group of grasscutters with reference to

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the nature of feed taken in. Xicatto *et al.*, (2003) had reported that caecal fermentation increases as a consequence of increased intake of solid feed.

The entire (GIT) weight in this study that ranged from 2.77 to 4.07% are less than the value of 8.30% recorded by Olomu *et al.*, (2003) and the value range of 5-10.2% recorded by Henry *et al.* (2012). The variation observed in this study with that of other authors could be attributed to the ages the animals were slaughtered.

The weights of the liver, kidneys, heart, spleen and gall bladders expressed as percentages of live body weight were similar whereas that of the lungs and pancreas were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different. The weight of the liver obtained (1.19-1.63%) is in agreement with value of 1.42-1.47% (Henry *et al.*, 2012) but slightly less than 1.7-1.8% reported by (Olomu *et al.*, 2003). The kidneys weight 0.25-0.34% are in harmony with 0.28%-0.33% (Olomu *et al.*, 2003) but less than 0.38-0.49% (Henry *et al.*, 2012). The values of weight of the lungs (0.52 to 0.87%) are comparable to 0.56 to 0.69% (Henry *et al.*, 2012) and 0.62 to 0.67% (Olomu *et al.*, 2003). The heart weights recorded 0.39 to 0.48% are in line with 0.44-0.50% (Olomu *et al.*, 2003), but less than 0.56 to 0.67% (Henry *et al.*, 2012).

The Pancreas weight which ranged in this study from 0.03-0.045 was significantly ($P < 0.05$) different. The average spleen weights 0.08-0.155% is less than 0.27-0.34% (Olomu *et al.*, 2003). The weight of the gall bladder obtained ranged 0.04-0.065% were not significantly influence by the feeding regimes. These results shows that none of the visceral organs in the experimental grasscutters, were damaged by the feeding regimes since most organs were comparable to other researcher's reports. It is known that these organs help to ascertain the health status of farm animals. Liver size is known to increase in response to several factors especially deficiency of amino acids (Carew, 1981). It was observed in this study that, this feeding regimes up to 9% of their weekly body live weight did not compromise the health status negatively. There was no record of loss of any grasscutters in any treatment neither was there any sign of distress among the grasscutters.

Conclusion

The health status of growing grasscutters in terms of excess elongation/enlargement (as indicated in the morphometric indices, the weight of the (GIT) and Visceral organs weights were not negatively affected by concentrate supplementation of fresh wilted grass diets. It is therefore recommended that, growing grasscutters on a basal diet of fresh wilted grass, such as elephant grass, should be supplemented with concentrate diet (18% CP; 2700 kcal/kg) at the daily rate of 5% of body weight.

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